

Studies on Stability and Electrokinetic Potential of Sulphur Hydrosol

B. N. Ghosh and Arun Kumar Gangopadhyay

A fairly pure and stable sulphur hydrosol has been prepared by a slight modification of von Janck's method with a view to ascertaining the existence of any relation between stability and electrokinetic potential. The true zeta-potential of the sol found for rapid coagulation from electro-osmotic data is 31.3 mv, while that found for slow coagulation both by electro-osmotic and electrophoretic methods is 38.4 mv.

A correction for surface conductance, which is quite marked in this case, has been applied by using an equation of the form :

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + m \frac{1}{S}$$

A given rate of coagulation of the sol is characterised by a definite value of the true zeta-potential, independent of the valency of the counter ions used.

Attempts were made in the past to correlate the stability of a colloid with its electrical charge or the potential of the electrical double layer. Experimental results of Powis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 734), Mukherjee *et al.* (this *Journal*, 1928, 5, 735), Kruyt *et al.* (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 130, 170), and Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2693) on As_2S_3 sol, and also of Kruyt *et al.* (*Kolloid Z.*, 1937, 78, 32) and Weiser *et al.* (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, 42, 119) on AgI and other sols do not support either Hardy's theory (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1900 A66, 110) of coagulation at the isoelectric point or Powis' theory (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1915, 89, 186) of coagulation at a critical potential. According to Hermans (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, 36, 133), Verwey and Overbeek ("Theory of the Stability of Lyophobic Colloids", 1948), Rutgers (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, 36, 69), Bikerman (*ibid.*, 1940, 36, 154) and others an error of the order of 100% or more may occur in calculating the zeta-potential by the Smoluchowski equation (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1918, 93, 129).

Rutgers (*loc. cit.*) has shown that the true zeta-potential (ζ) of a uniform glass capillary wall of radius 'r' in contact with a very dilute electrolyte solution or in water can be determined by the following formula :

$$\zeta = \frac{4\pi r \eta}{D} \cdot S \cdot \frac{E_1}{P} \left(1 + \frac{2\chi}{rS} \right) = \zeta_1 \left(1 + \frac{2\chi}{rS} \right) \quad \dots (1)$$

where E_1 = streaming potential, P = the pressure used for streaming the liquid through the capillary, χ = the specific surface conductance, and S = the specific conductance of the liquid in bulk.

Overbeek and Wijga (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1946, 65, 556) have shown that equation (1) holds for a single glass capillary, but fails in the case of a porous diaphragm made of powdered glass particles.

Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 274, 393) has shown from Wijga's data on streaming potential of powdered pyrex and Jena glass diaphragms that the true zeta-potential can be calculated from the equation :

$$\zeta = \zeta_a \left(1 + \frac{2\alpha \chi}{Sr} \right) \quad (2)$$

where α is a correction factor for the diaphragm.

Recently, Ghosh (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, 49, 1977) has deduced the following expression for the true zeta-potential of the particles of As_2S_3 sol in the form of a diaphragm, which has been further verified by Ghosh and Rakshit (*Science & Culture*, 1953, 18, 498) and others on a number of different colloids :

$$\zeta/\zeta_a = 1 + \frac{3\chi}{aR} \cdot \frac{1}{S} \quad \dots (3)$$

where R = radius of the spherical particles forming the diaphragm, a = the ratio of the volume V_2 of liquid to the volume V_1 of solid in the diaphragm, χ = the specific surface conductance, S = the bulk conductance of the supernatant solution, and ζ_a = the apparent ζ -potential calculated by using Smoluchowski's equation from electro-osmotic data.

Ghosh has further shown that equation (3) can be expressed in the following form :

$$\zeta/\zeta_a = 1 + \frac{3r}{2aR} \left(\frac{2\chi}{rS} \right) = 1 + \frac{3V_1 r}{2V_2 R} \left(\frac{2\chi}{rS} \right) \quad \dots (3a)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \zeta/\zeta_a = 1 + \alpha \left(\frac{2\chi}{rS} \right) \quad \dots (3b)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + m \cdot \frac{1}{S} \quad \dots (4)$$

where $\alpha = 3r/2aR$ and r is the average radius of a typical pore in the diaphragm, and $m = (2\alpha\chi)/r\zeta$.

For electrophoresis, when (Ka) is large (K is the reciprocal of the thickness of the double layer and a is the radius of the particles), Ghosh *et al.* (*Nature*, 1955, 176, 1081) have shown that the expressions of Booth (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, 44, 455) and Henry (*ibid.*, 1948, 44, 1021) reduce to the form :

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + m^1 \cdot \frac{1}{S} \quad \dots (5)$$

where $m^1 = \chi/R\zeta$. They have also shown for a number of sols that corresponding to a given rate of coagulation by electrolytes, there is a definite value of true zeta-potential, independent of the valency of the counter ions used.

A systematic investigation has been undertaken to ascertain if a similar relation between true zeta-potential and rate of coagulation also holds in the case of sulphur hydrosol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Among the various methods of preparing hydrosol of sulphur the present authors tried those of Odén (*Z. Chem. Ind. Koll.*, 1911, 8, 186), Ostwald and Egger (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 43, 353), and von Weimarn and Malyschew (*ibid.*, 1911, 8, 216), but could not obtain a fairly stable and concentrated sol. A slight modification of von Janek's method (*ibid.*, 1933, 64, 31), however, furnished a hydrosol of the desired quality.

Preparation of the Sol

The standard solutions used for preparation of the sulphur hydrosol were : (a) 72 g./litre of Na_2SO_3 solution ; (b) 128 g./litre of $Na_2S \cdot 9H_2O$ solution ; (c) 270 g./litre of H_2SO_4 (d 1.84) ; (d) H_2SO_4 (d 1.84). All solutions were prepared from E. Merck's guaranteed reagent.

To 1000 c.c. of solution (b), taken in a 2-litre pyrex flask and cooled in a bath of ice-cold water, 30 c.c. of solution (a) was added. To 970 c.c. of solution of (a), taken in a 4-litre pyrex flask, also cooled in a bath of ice-cold water, about 60 c.c. of H_2SO_4 (conc.) was added in small instalments with constant stirring. About 160 c.c. of solution (c) was then added dropwise to the mixture of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}-\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_3$ solution with frequent stirring till a permanent turbidity just appeared. This solution was then poured into the mixture of $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_3-\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and shaken vigorously, when an opaque, yellowish white sol was formed. It was allowed to stand for 1 hour in an ice-cold water bath when most of the sulphur particles separated at the bottom. The solution was filtered through a fluted filter paper, the residue washed, and finally peptised with conductivity water (about 1,000 c.c.). The sol thus formed was dialysed for 7 days in cellophane bags against conductivity water. About 6 litres of the sol was thus prepared and allowed to age for 15 days. In this period the bigger particles settled to the bottom and the middle portion was siphoned off and collected in another Jena flask. The sol thus prepared was negatively charged and moderately stable; its pH was 4.45.

Equicoagulating Concentration of Electrolytes

The concentrations of different electrolytes, which coagulated a colloid at a given rate, have been termed as the equicoagulating concentrations.

The electrolytes used for coagulation were: NaCl , MgCl_2 , AlCl_3 , mixture of $\text{NaCl} + \text{MgCl}_2$, $\text{NaCl} + \text{AlCl}_3$. Four pairs of clean and dry test tubes of equal size were arranged in two rows (4 in each row) in a stand. The test tubes were marked from '1' to '4' (in one of the row). Into each of the marked test tubes different amounts (2c.c. or less) of an electrolyte of a definite strength were added and the volume in each test tube was made to 2 c.c. by addition of conductivity water (where necessary). Two c.c. of the sol was taken into each of the test tubes kept in the other row. Finally, the electrolyte in the test tube marked '1' was poured into the opposite test tube containing the sulphur sol. The sol-electrolyte mixture was poured back to the test tube marked '1', which was corked and allowed to stand for 30 minutes. In the same way, the electrolytes taken in the other test tubes were mixed with the sol and allowed to stand for 30 minutes. As there was no sharp separation of a clear meniscus, the sol-electrolyte mixture was centrifuged for 2 minutes at a definite speed after allowing it to stand for 30 minutes. The supernatant solution was examined for transparency for determining the equicoagulating concentration of the electrolyte. A large number of experiments was performed for determining accurately the equicoagulating concentrations with different electrolytes.

The same method was followed for determining the equicoagulating concentrations of electrolytes when the rate of coagulation was slow, *i.e.*, boundary separation occurred after 24 hours.

Electro-osmotic Experiments

A definite volume (200 c.c.) of the sol was taken in a clean and dry Jena bottle (500 c.c. capacity) and to it was added an equal volume of an electrolyte of requisite strength; the mixture was allowed to stand for 30 mins. and 24 hrs. for the rapid and slow rates of coagulation respectively. The coagula separating from the supernatant liquid after centrifuging were transferred into a 'U' tube, which was then centrifuged at a definite speed whereby a compact diaphragm was formed. The electro-osmotic velocity was measured by the moving bubble method of Mukherjee *et al* (this *Journal*, 1927, 4, 493).

The experiments were performed at 25° . The distance between the two electrodes and the mass of coagula, and the volume it occupied in the U-tube were kept constant. To minimise resistance

to the flow of liquid, the side tubes and the stopcocks were so selected as to have sufficiently wide bore; the length of the air bubble in the horizontal tube was about 0.4 cm. These precautions were necessary for maintaining some of the variable factors constant.

The extrapolated values of the true zeta-potential of sulphur hydrosol in the regions of rapid and slow rates of coagulation were found to be 31.3 mv and 38.4 mv.

TABLE I

Electro-osmosis of sulphur hydrosol (rapid coagulation).

Time for coagulation = 30 minutes. Temp. = 25°.

$$1/\zeta = 0.032 \text{ mv. } \zeta = 31.3 \text{ mv. } m = \frac{2\alpha\chi}{\zeta_r} = 6.287 \times 10^{-5}.$$

Electrolyte used.	Equicoag. conc.	Supernatant solution.		Calculated values of ζ_a from	
		pH.	S (mhos cm. ⁻¹) × 10 ⁴ .	Smoluchowski's eq.*	eq. (4)**
NaCl	5.54 × 10 ⁻⁴ N	3.50	515.50	30.3 mv	30.1 mv
NaCl & MgCl ₂	4.08 × 10 ⁻³ & 6.59 × 10 ⁻³	3.62	13.96	12.8	13.0
MgCl ₂	6.59 × 10 ⁻³	3.52	9.00	8.0	9.3
NaCl & AlCl ₃	1.63 × 10 ⁻³ & 1.60 × 10 ⁻³	3.70	11.12	11.2	11.3
NaCl & AlCl ₃	1.30 × 10 ⁻³ & 1.62 × 10 ⁻³	3.70	4.81	6.2	6.2
AlCl ₃	1.65 × 10 ⁻³	3.62	3.58	4.9	4.8

* From electro-osmotic data.

** Using the values of ζ and m .

TABLE II

Electro-osmotic data of sulphur hydrosol at 25° (slow coagulation).

$$1/\zeta = 0.026. \zeta = 38.4 \text{ mv. } m = \frac{2\alpha\chi}{\zeta_r} = 4.814 \times 10^{-5}.$$

Electrolyte used.	Equicoag. conc.	Supernatant solution.		Calculated values of ζ_a from	
		pH.	S (mhos cm. ⁻¹) × 10 ⁴ .	Smoluchowski's eq.*	eq. (2)**
NaCl	1.87 × 10 ⁻⁴ N	3.55	189.90	34.4 mv	35.0 mv
NaCl & MgCl ₂	4.89 × 10 ⁻³ & 4.26 × 10 ⁻³	3.60	12.14	15.4	15.2
NaCl & MgCl ₂	1.63 × 10 ⁻³ & 4.18 × 10 ⁻³	3.60	8.34	12.1	12.0
MgCl ₂	4.00 × 10 ⁻³	3.60	6.57	10.2	10.1
AlCl ₃	1.39 × 10 ⁻³	3.60	3.33	5.8	5.8

* From electro-osmotic data.

** Using the values of ζ and m .

In the rapid and slow rates of coagulation, the pH of the supernatant solutions with different electrolytes remained within 3.50 to 3.70 and 3.55 to 3.60 respectively. Tables I and II show that the effect of surface conductance is appreciable. The values of the apparent zeta-potential varied from 4.9 to 30.3 mv and 5.8 to 34.4 mv for rapid and slow rates respectively.

Electrophoretic Experiments

These experiments were carried out at 25° in a modified form of Burton's U-tube apparatus (Ghosh *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, p. 1081). Reversible Ag, AgCl electrodes were used and the electrolytes selected contained Cl⁻ as anion.

Preparation of the Colloid-electrolyte Mixture.—The sulphur hydrosol (40 c.c.) was mixed with the electrolyte (40 c.c.) of desired strength; the mixture was allowed to stand for 28 minutes and then centrifuged for 2 minutes at a definite speed. The big particles settled at the bottom; the rest of the colloid-electrolyte mixture was decanted and used for filling the lower part and funnel of the U-tube.

Preparation of the Supernatant Liquid.—The sol (200 c.c.) was mixed with the electrolyte (200 c.c.) of desired strength in a Jena bottle and allowed to stand for 24 hours. The mixture was centrifuged for 3 minutes at a definite speed to furnish a clear supernatant liquid, which was stored in a Jena bottle and used for filling the upper part of the U-tube and the electrode vessels communicating with the limbs of the U-tube through ground-glass joints. The coagula, which remained in the centrifuging tubes, were used for preparation of the diaphragm required for electro-osmotic experiments.

The distance moved by the colloid boundary under a given current in a given time was measured. The mean value of the upward and downward movement of the boundary was taken for calculation of ζ , by Smoluchowski's equation. The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Electrophoresis of sulphur hydrosol (slow coagulation).

Time for coagulation = 24 hours. Temp. = 25°.

$$1/\zeta = 0.026 \text{ mv. } \zeta = 38.4 \text{ mv. } m^1 = \frac{\chi}{\zeta r} = 1.885 \times 10^{-5}$$

Electrolyte used.	Equicoag. conc.	S_1 of supernat. soln. (mhos cm ⁻¹).	S_2 of sol-electrolyte mixture (mhos cm ⁻¹).	Calculated values of ζ , from	
				Electrophoretic data using Smoluchowski's eq.	eq. (3) using the value of ζ and m^1 .
NaCl	$1.87 \times 10^{-3} N$	185.23×10^{-4}	192.09×10^{-4}	36.5 mv	37.0 mv
NaCl & MgCl ₂	4.89×10^{-3} & 4.26×10^{-3}	12.58	12.41	24.0	24.3
NaCl & MgCl ₂	1.63×10^{-3} & 4.18×10^{-3}	8.45	8.48	21.0	20.8
MgCl ₂	4.00×10^{-3}	6.46	6.52	18.0	18.2

DISCUSSION

It is noticed from columns (3) of Tables I and II that the pH's of the supernatant solutions with different electrolytes for rapid and slow rates of coagulation remain within 3.50 to 3.70 and 3.55 to 3.60 respectively.

From the data recorded in columns (4) and (5) of Tables I and II and columns (3), (4), (5) of Table III, the values of $1/S$ and $1/\zeta_a$ have been calculated; when these are plotted a straight line is obtained in every case. The value of m has been found from the slope of the straight line and the true ζ from the intercept of the straight line on the $1/\zeta_a$ axis.

It appears from Table I that the effect of surface conductance is appreciable. The values of ζ_a for rapid rate of coagulation for different electrolytes varied from 4.9 to 30.3 mv. The ζ_a values for different electrolytes are evaluated by means of equation (4) and are compared with ζ_a values obtained from electro-osmotic data using Smoluchowski's equation. It is evident from the data in columns (5) and (6), that the values of ζ_a found from electro-osmotic data using Smoluchowski's equation do not differ appreciably (except for $MgCl_2$) from the corresponding values calculated by means of equation (4).

Tables II and III evidently show that the effect of surface conductance is also appreciable both for electrophoretic and electro-osmotic methods in the region of slow coagulation, the effect in the latter method being more marked.

Again, the values of ζ_a for different electrolytes, calculated by equations (4) and (5) from electro-osmotic and electrophoretic data respectively for the slow rate of coagulation, agree well (cf. columns 5 and 6 in Tables II & III) with the corresponding ζ_a values, calculated from experimental data using the Smoluchowski equation.

The true zeta-potential (ζ), calculated both from electro-osmotic and electrophoretic data, is 38.4 mv for the slow rate of coagulation while that found for rapid rate of coagulation is 31.3 mv.

The true zeta-potential of sulphur hydrosol depends therefore on the rate of coagulation, the more rapid the rate, the smaller it is in magnitude.

In conclusion it may be pointed out, that a fairly pure sulphur hydrosol possesses an appreciable surface conductance.

The authors express their grateful thanks to the C. S. I. R. for a research grant.